

THE "THE WORLD ACCORDING TO GARP" BY J. IRVING AS BILDUNGSROMAN OF THE 1970S IN AMERICAN LITERATURE

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Abstract

This article analyzes the prerequisites for the development and formation of personality in the novel "The World Through the Eyes of Garp" by the famous writer of the 20th century J. Irving. The question of the influence of Ch. Dickens' novels in the creation of the main image of the novel is also considered. The World According to Garp is a Bildungsroman, which is a chronological account of a life. It is complex and episodic, with subplots such as the dissolution of traditional gender roles, infidelity, assaults on women, and death. Other themes include the challenges of becoming an artist, the difficulties of becoming an artist, and death.

Keywords: Bildungsroman, novel, personality, formation, development, theme, plot

"Novel of development" is what the German word "bildungsroman" implies. A bildungsroman is a book that tracks the growth of a young person. A novel of education, in its simplest form, is a story that chronicles the progressive psychological and physical growth of a male or female character from infancy to adulthood, or the point at which the character finds his position in society. Circumstances, obstacles, and environment all have a significant impact on how the main literary character develops. The novel's distinguishing characteristic is the hero's successful completion of his positive life agenda. Coming-of-age stories frequently include orphans as the primary protagonists, who struggle with various difficulties throughout their lives. Against this backdrop, supporting characters influence the hero's development in an illuminating, detrimental, or constructive way [3, p. 37-38]. Jane Eyre (1847) by Charlotte Bronte, Great Expectations (1861) by Charles Dickens, The Adventures of Huckleberry Finn (1884) by Mark Twain, The Catcher in the Rye (1951) by J.D. Salinger, To Kill a Mockingbird (1960), and other works by these authors are considered classic types of Bildungsroman.

Midway through the 1970s, a consolidation phase started. Following the end of the Vietnam War, the US swiftly recognized the People's Republic of China and commemorated its bicentennial. Soon afterward came the 1980s, sometimes known as the "Me Decade," in which individuals prioritized little social concerns over more significant ones.

Old literary traditions continued, although there was less support for pure innovation. Novels by up-and-coming writers like John Gardner, John Irving (The World According to Garp, 1978), Paul Theroux (The Mosquito Coast, 1982), William Kennedy (Ironweed, 1983), and Alice Walker (The Color Purple, 1982) were exquisitely written in terms of style and portrayed heartfelt human tragedies. Again, realistic topics, situations, and characters raised questions. Realism was abandoned by experimental authors in the 1960s, but it began to slowly reemerge. A novel-within-a-novel structure or black American vernacular, as in John Gardner's October Light (1976) or Alice Walker's

The Color Purple, were commonly blended with it. Minority literature grew in popularity. Dramatizations that were more cinematic and vibrant replaced realistic drama. However, the "Me Decade" was also reflected in the audacious new writers Jay McInerney, Bret Easton Ellis, and Tama Janowitz (Bright Lights, Big City, 1984). 1986's Slaves of New York.[5]

John Winslow Irving (1942) is a famous American-Canadian novelist, short story writer, and screenwriter.[4] Irving gained praise from both critics and the general public after The World According to Garp became a worldwide hit in 1978. The Hotel New Hampshire (1981), The Cider House Rules (1985), A Prayer for Owen Meany (1989), and A Widow for One Year (1998) are just a few of Irving's books that have enjoyed successful sales. He received the Academy Award for Best Adapted Screenplay at the 72nd Academy Awards (1999) for his screenplay for The Cider House Rules. The World According to Garp, John Irving's fourth book, is about a man born out of wedlock to a feminist activist who goes on to become a writer. After its 1978 release, the book enjoyed years of best-seller status. For the 1979 National Book Award, it was a finalist.

Garp's adolescence and his growth as a person and artist are at the core of the narrative. In a bildungsroman, the main character learns about the highs and lows of life via his interactions with the many people he meets and the connections he forms. Garp learns about women via his relationships with his mother, Cushie Percy, Helen Holm, Charlotte, the Austrian woman who fell, Alice Fletcher, Mrs. Ralph, and Ellen James. He has learned precious lessons about love, accountability, discipline, suffering, and hope from his duties as a husband and parent. While Ellen Jamesian and Pooh Percy despise him, John Wolf and Roberta Muldoon are friendly to him. Despite being only 33 years old, Garp has a busy life.

A Bildungsroman, sometimes known as a fictitious biography or coming-of-age story of a single protagonist (who typically develops into an artist), is essentially what The World According to Garp is. One of them is the book David Copperfield by Charles Dickens. Even Jane Eyre would fit the bill because the novel

details her dreadful upbringing and years spent in school prior to meeting Mr. Rochester. The World According to Garp demonstrates this. The main character of the story is T.S. Garp, the artistically talented son of an asexual feminist nurse who had him with a dying, lobotomized technical sergeant while she was caring for him. The book follows Garp as he studies at the esteemed Steering School (where his mother works as a nurse), competes in wrestling, visits Austria, and discovers and his desire to be a writer.

The creation of Garp marks the start of the book. *Lunacy and Sorrow: The Life and Art of T.S. Garp*, written by a biographer, serves as the primary narrative voice. Jenny served as a nurse at a Boston hospital during World War II. Jenny uses the body of a wounded soldier with mental impairment to conceive. She had a soldier, Technical Sergeant Garp, and he passes away immediately after she acts selfishly. After the soldier, Jenny gave her kid the name T.S. Garp. Her son ultimately enrolls and decides he wants to work at The Steering School, where Jenny later finds a position.

Garp falls in love with Helen Holm, whose father is the school's wrestling coach. She warns him that until he develops into a true writer, she won't marry him. Following graduation, Garp relocates to Vienna, Austria, with the idea that in order to become a writer, he must have life experience. As she works on her memoirs, *A Sexual Suspect*, Jenny is with him. Helen has consented to marry Garp, and he has completed a novella titled *The Pension Grillparzer*. Garp travels to America with his mother to look for book publishers. With the help of editor John Wolf, Jenny's book becomes a best-seller, and she gains notoriety in the feminism community. One cult that idolizes her is called the Ellen James Society after an eleven-year-old girl who was raped and had her tongue cut off by the rapist. Jenny, who is now financially secure thanks to the popularity of her book, gives up nursing and moves in with her parents in Dog's Head Harbor, New Hampshire, where she operates a shelter for battered women. Robert Muldoon, a former professional football player who is now transgender and goes by the name Roberta, also has admiration for Jenny.

Garp has his book published as well, but he does not experience the same level of success as his mother. Garp stays at home to take care of their two young kids, Walt and Duncan, while Helen accepts a position as a professor of English literature. *Procrastination and The World According to Bensenhaver* are two novels that Garp has completed. The Ellen James Society and other feminists criticize the latter because it features vividly violent assault scenes. As a result of Garp's many extramarital romances during their marriage, Helen decides to have a relationship with one of her doctoral students, Michael Milton. One night, as Michael and Helen are having sex in Helen's car, Garp arrives in his car with his boys and strikes the car driveway. In the accident, the younger child perishes and his brother

loses an eye. Jenny becomes Garp and Helen's third child when they are able to mend their differences.

A few months later, a guy who blames Jenny Fields' book for the dissolution of his marriage violently murders her. Only women and children, according to her supporters, will be allowed to attend her funeral, so with Roberta's help, Garp assumes the identity of a woman to participate in the ceremonies. Garp's actual identity is exposed at the funeral, after which he leaves for the airport. At the airport, he bumps across Ellen James, who has grown up and become a lady. She tells Garp that she hates the group that bears her name and that she agrees wholeheartedly with the way he describes assault in his book. Ellen travels with Garp and is welcomed into the family.

Roberta insists that Garp establish The Fields Foundation, a charitable organization, in honor of his mother. When he gets back, he is named the wrestling coach at The Steering School. One day while practicing his wrestling, Pooh Percy, a member of the Ellen James Society, kills Garp. When they were younger, Pooh and Garp were friends, and Pooh now believes that Garp killed her sister. According to the epilogue, Garp's final book, *My Father's Illusions*, will be released as a result of his son's efforts.

The World According to Garp is a Bildungsroman, thus as a chronological account of a life, it tends to be lengthy on character development and short on plot, although this is more or less expected. Typically, the storyline is complicated and episodic, with everything leading up to the character's success or failure. The dissolution of traditional gender roles in families, infidelity, assaults on women, and death are just a few of the many subplots in *The World According to Garp*. Other themes include the challenges of becoming an artist (and the ambivalence many artists feel about whether creating art is even a worthwhile endeavor), the difficulties of becoming an artist, and death.

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